

SUSTAINING CITIES, NATURALLY

Webinar summary & key messages (13-14 Oct. 2022)

A joint webinar of 4 collaboration projects focusing on urban restoration in Europe, China and Latin America

[Link to recordings, resources and slides](#)

Introduction

Urbanisation is one of the key drivers for degrading ecosystems. By 2030, cities are expected to cover three times as much land as they did in 2000, with much of the expansion occurring in biodiversity hotspots. By 2050 two-thirds of the world's population will live in cities.

The UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration, running from 2021 through to 2030, aims to massively scale up the restoration of degraded and destroyed ecosystems as a proven measure to fight climate change and enhance food security, water supply and biodiversity. The current post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework calls for at least 20% of degraded freshwater, marine and terrestrial ecosystems to be restored by 2030. Similarly, the EU proposes a legally binding regulation on nature restoration that explicitly targets the restoration of Europe's nature, to repair the 80% of European habitats that are in poor condition, and to bring back nature to all ecosystems, from forest and agricultural land to marine, freshwater and urban ecosystems. For all cities, towns and suburbs, the nature restoration law proposes targets for “no net loss” urban green space and urban tree canopy

cover by 2030 and the increase of green urban spaces in cities, towns and suburbs from 2040 onwards. However, targets for new green space in European cities, towns and suburbs do not kick in until 2040. Can we afford to wait?

This webinar aimed to bring together science and practice from across China, Latin America and Europe to present and debate aspects that are imperative if we are to succeed in developing high quality urban nature restoration at scale. The webinar dives into key aspects in dedicated sessions involving economics, policy, governance and institutional issues, social aspects, education and awareness, environmental quality and ecological quality of restoration activities.

Economics of NBS and restoration

NBS in cities provide largely public or common goods and services with limited revenue streams such as heat mitigation, flood mitigation or recreation, health and wellbeing. The location of NBS matters for who gets to profit from NBS, which is essential for social resilience and social equity. Detailed understanding of these benefits is lacking.

NBS needs to be exponentially scaled up to meet the policy priorities of the European Green Deal and also to meet the needs in Latin America and China.

But it's not evident to create 'markets for NBS' and it is difficult to predict reliably the commercial

prospects of NBS, which makes financing of NBS projects challenging, especially when wanting to involve the private sector.

Despite increasing prominence of NBS in scientific and policy arenas, knowledge and evidence about benefits, costs and financial performance of NBS remain scattered and not easily accessible. The same goes for functioning financing and incentive mechanisms. The way we think about 'business cases for NBS' should include a careful understanding of what is the role of public versus private sector in securing public or common goods.

Talks were from different angles about how economic and impact valuation of NBS can and should make a difference in Latin America and the Caribbean region (Lili Ilieva, UNEP), insights from an economic benefit analysis of heat mitigation benefits in Paris (Tim Taylor, REGREEN) and about limits to markets for NBS with perspectives from European and Latin American cases (David Barton, INTERLACE) and finally, a talk on the vital role that NBS can and should play in a nature positive economy (Daniela Rizzi, REGREEN, CONEXUS). **Key messages from talks:**

- **Global investments in NBS need to at least triple by 2030** in order to meet climate change, biodiversity and land degradation targets, but with only 14% of investment into the NBS market currently coming from the private sector, there's a real **need and challenge to both increase the share of private investment and the total volume of NBS investment.**
- The general language of business case for NBS can crowd out what are the main mechanisms of securing and enhancing ecosystem services in an urban context. **We need to use the discourse of business cases critically and at the appropriate moment.** In other settings we need to use a discourse of social-ecological systems, stewardship on common property management.
- With the wide impacts of NBS it is important to get a handle on how we can **value NBS benefits to put them into a policy context** and to think through different ways that we can capture the values of NBS benefits through for instance Payment for Ecosystem Services or other metrics.
- **Valuing the economic benefits of NBS**

requires interdisciplinary approaches for both understanding what concrete impacts green infrastructure has on e.g. cooling a city and what this does to e.g. human health and wellbeing.

- **A nature positive economy requires a paradigm shift** advanced through standards for high quality NBS, measurement and valuation of NBS impacts and benefits, multi-level, cross-sectoral policy framework, significantly increased investments in NBS, development of sector support and capacity building and awareness raising among businesses, policy makers and the public.

Policy, governance and institutional issues

Much research has been conducted on nature-based solutions and their potential to provide multiple benefits and address various societal challenges such as climate change and promote a nature-friendly economy. Thus, the evidence and knowledge about NBS is constantly expanding. However, to put this knowledge and NBS into practice in our cities, we need policy and institutional frameworks that support and promote NBS across sectors and scales.

This raises questions such as: What governance and policy tools exist and have proven effective in promoting NBS/restoration, and can they potentially be replicated in other cities? What role might NBS standards play in this regard, and are cities already receiving the support and guidance they need to implement NBS themselves? What are the potential challenges in Europe and Latin America in creating an effective policy framework and increased collaboration with various stakeholders in the governance of NBS and restoration? And is the mainstreaming of NBS merely wishful thinking? **These issues were discussed in this session and the following key messages were derived:**

Framing NBS Mainstreaming

- ...is challenging and **risks diluting the values and integrity of NBS**; therefore, it is critical to always ensure quality standards
- ...**requires overcoming silos** in public administration and developing a holistic policy rather than just integrating NBS into policy

- ...needs **new narratives that are created collaboratively** to make the term more accessible to target stakeholders and implementing communities and to prioritize green and blue NBS

Achievements and challenges ahead:

- Knowledge about NBS has increased, efforts have been centralized, and several guidelines are available, but it is **critical to translate this new knowledge into action**.
- The mindset of practitioners and local governments has changed, and there is increased collaboration between departments, but this is not enough to keep up with the pace of global challenges, and we **need buy-in and commitment from the high political level to address nature, climate, and resilience holistically**.
- There are still many different regulations that are unable to adapt to emerging challenges and collaborations, which need to be adapted to **allow for more flexibility**.
- Citizen voices have become more important (especially in Latin America), but the 'Invisibles' need to be made more visible and the **cycles and timelines of policy, research, and citizens need to be better aligned**.

Social aspects

Urban contexts for NBS present a fascinating range of opportunities, challenges and avenues for people, both in terms of engagement and social cohesion, but also as regards the ways in which those relationships develop and how these impacts on success or failure of NBS. The complexity of land ownership, fragmentation of habitats, and historical community development all add vital nuances that differ greatly from rural settings. New green deals and environmental sustainability programmes tend to call for greater justice and inclusivity in addressing global challenges including action on climate and biodiversity. Co-creation has been central to many NBS programmes and initiatives, in Europe, China and Latin America. But as the EU's State of the Art in NBS report highlights, participatory or co-design processes should not automatically be considered as a means through which social inclusion can be fostered.

This session involved targeted interventions showing how NBS projects have made progress in

integrating local citizen knowledge with scientific evidence and other data. These examples indicate how cities can achieve more just and sustainable social and ecological outcomes through NBS in the urban myriad of complex, evolving and exciting environments. Here, links can be made with the economics and governance strands, too. David Barton (INTERLACE) highlighted the valuable benefits of NBS but also that there is a risk in overplaying the business models language, especially around nature-based economies. It is important to stress that not all places are the same e.g. NBS funding by the private sector is difficult in market failure settings (Wild et al, 2017) which make these very different contexts to thriving business districts or capital city centres. This raises the importance and value of case study information from a broader range of contexts, as stressed by McKenna Davis. INTERLACE is seeking to address this theme through its Urban Governance Atlas of practical tools instruments and lessons.

Likewise, CONEXUS is preparing an integrative 'ecosystem of guidelines', based on two-way learning between Latin America and Europe, drawing on a wide review of guidance resources and users' perspectives of these assets. Common to both examples is the dominance of legal, regional and strategic approaches and the need for more local participation stories, as highlighted by Diana Wiesner. Efrén Feliu Torres called for greater emphasis on the quality and standardisation of NBS models.

Johannes Langemeyer (INTERLACE) provided an inspiring view as to how we might develop and strengthen delivery against the three aspects of environmental justice. Weaving notions of justice with ecosystem services in this way can provide a practicable framework for cities to address the distributive, procedural and recognition justice qualities that should be central to NBS programmes. These themes were later picked up by Manuel Wolff (CLEARING HOUSE) in sharing ideas for the creation of more inclusive and biodiverse networks of NBS within a broader city-wide framing. Erika Calderon (INTERLACE) provided practical examples of implementation in dense deprived neighbourhoods to improve environmental justice and social cohesion. Arjen Buijs (CONEXUS) gave insights into how projects can both strengthen data on governance of NBS and use these processes to enhance evidence on NBS performance. Their work has set out key characteristics for more inclusive

and participatory impact assessment frameworks whilst establishing more nuanced processes for engaging with city politics and citizen's priorities on the ground. **The following key messages were derived from this session:**

- The social dimension is strongly interlinked with the governance theme, highlighting the **importance of supporting governance structures** and initiatives that enable the consideration of just and inclusive consideration and genuine participatory processes in the co-creation, -planning and -maintenance of NBS
- There is **shift in norms of how we think about valuation** embracing multiple/plural values in the assessment of NBS, giving more weight to aspects of environmental justice and people's perception as well as to the interplay of perceived social networks and biological networks
- Co-creation processes are not always inclusive, which risks increasing rather than reducing social and environmental injustices. A specific **challenge is to include marginalised groups** and dwellers in deprived, dense urban districts, which are dealing with different challenges (e.g. waste management, lacking infrastructure, safety, homelessness). Building on established relations and trust, the joint planning and implementation of NBS cannot help solving such challenges and improve human health and well-being.

Education

In the wise words of Nelson Mandela: "Education is the most powerful weapon which you can use to change the world." Better awareness of the opportunities, benefits and limitations of NBS has been identified by citizens and experts as one of the main factors that could facilitate the transition to more sustainable cities and territories. Not only can education help to build capacities and new knowledge, it can also increase support for NBS and thus the involvement of citizens and other valuable stakeholder groups in their co-creation, financing and maintenance. As such, this session discussed the current state of NBS education, gaps to be filled, the challenges to mainstreaming NBS in education and how to better support NBS educators. **A selection of key challenges and potential solutions to help overcome these include:**

- **Time and resource constraints:** new proposed materials, approaches and tools around NBS

need to be designed to complement and fit seamlessly into current curricula without creating extra work for the educators. This can be supported by co-producing materials with the schools/educators to address their needs, identify entry points and ensure the best fit and timing within current frameworks; make financing available for e.g. initial IT investments, event organisation, capacity building, external facilitators, etc.

- **Lack of buy-in for NBS as a new thematic area:** adopt a personal approach to sit with schools and educators to present holistic benefits of NBS, answer questions, and draw attention to the multiple benefits beyond single-topic curricula from taking education 'outside the classroom' - eliminating the idea that the new topic will be an added burden for the schools/educators; highlight the diversity of potential career opportunities that can result from an NBS-centered education path
- **Limited expertise amongst educators and schools about NBS:** encourage collaboration and exchange of expertise between the schools, teachers, policy makers and higher education institutions to create a community of practice for ongoing learning; provide training programmes for teachers that do not add to their burden (i.e. they need to learn about NBS in their free time), but rather supports their own learning in an official capacity); utilise external facilitators to reduce pressure for teachers, bring new energy into the topic, and help educators increase their knowledge on the topic

In addition, new concepts, tools and materials tailored to different target groups (e.g. children, young people and their families, teachers as well as interested communities) and experiences with their application were presented. Examples include the 'City of Trees: Making trees and forest part of teaching at schools', Minecraft as a tool for engaging youth, Floormaps, Breathe Respirator Programme, augmented reality learning tours, Vigie-Nature School, and the Bioblitz citizen science initiative.

Environmental aspects

Urban areas see multiple societal challenges, including climate change, increasing urbanisation and loss of green space and biodiversity. Urban restoration engages ecosystems to deliver nature-based solutions that help to solve some of the environmental challenges: blue-green infrastructure

reduces heat, alleviates heavy rain, flooding and erosion, helps to conserve healthy and living soils, and reduces carbon dioxide and air pollution. This session will introduce the science behind these mechanisms, illustrated by examples by local authorities in China (CLEARING HOUSE, Impact of urban tree cover on heat island in Chinese cities, presented by Dr Jiali Jin & GhuangZhou Orchard Restoration Project, presented by Dr Juan Su), Europe (REGREEN, City Explorer Toolkit, presented by Dr Laurence Jones) and Latin America (CONEXUS, Sao Paulo Living Lab, presented by Dr Giulliano Maselli Locosselli). **These issues were discussed in this session and the following key messages were derived:**

- Environmental aspects generated by NBS are well-known but **are dependent on local conditions**. As such, they are time demanding to model, and global tools are not easy to build.
- There is a **need for more effective communication** between academics, cities and governments, on how to implement NBS as places where it matters most – tools and models can help, but depend on data quality and data availability. Particularly for social data, data at a local scale is unavailable.
- **Environmental aspects are highly socially important**, as the environmental benefits created by NBS improve people's living environment.

Ecological quality of restoration activities

Ecological quality and applying nature-based solutions become all the more important when aiming to massively scale up restoration activities. It is important to establish guidance and principles for ensuring the quality of those restoration activities. This session presented scientific insights and experiences with how cities can recover and restore ecosystems, addressing what elements and processes are important for securing high quality urban nature and discussing why ecological quality matters in restoration activities.

Prof. Jun Yang (REGREEN) took the case of Beijing's new urban plain forests to discuss the challenges in introducing more biodiversity into dense, single layered and even age tree stand forest plantations, originally established to remove air pollution, counter urban heat island and sequester carbon. Beijing has established more than 1300km²

new urban plain forest over a period of 10 years, probably the largest urban NBS ever, but ecological conservation initiatives are yet to show results (e.g. restoring wetlands, diversifying tree stands, and creating habitats for animals) and will take time.

Marc Barra (REGREEN) showed a short, animated film on how to include ecological principles in urban NBS to increase biodiversity. The ban on using pesticides in 2017 in France in public spaces spurred a national interest in managing parks in more biodiverse-friendly way, resulting in a high demand for trainings and collaborations between cities. Marc Barra (REGREEN) subsequently provided insights into the main principles in ecological quality of green spaces using simple, but effective approaches, based on three pillars: increasing vegetation structure, increase the proportion of native species and reduce frequency of mowing. And talked about how more biodiverse ecosystems are better at delivering regulating services, e.g. drainage.

Dorá Almássy (Network Nature Expert) presented work undertaken for Network Nature on how to think about what are high-quality NBS: effectively implemented projects with limited negative impacts and properly addressed trade-offs that also address environmental justice and social cohesion. Key priority list of high quality NBS include: NBS needs to be maintained in the long term to secure benefits; be applicable in the local context and support biodiversity and ecosystem conservation.

Prof. Cheng Wang (CLEARINGHOUSE) reflected on the development in Chinese cities to work towards more biodiversity and green infrastructure: Connecting corridors between nature areas, restoration using minimum thresholds for native species, changing practices, albeit difficult, and collaborating with European cities and colleagues. The final panel debate reflected on what are the barriers for cities in changing the management of existing nature areas. **Key messages from the session on ecological quality in urban NBS:**

- **Perceived trade-offs between biodiversity and regulating ecosystem services** (e.g. heat regulation, air pollution regulation) can lead to large-scale NBS projects that do not follow ecological principles and result in biodiversity poor habitats. However, biodiversity rich forests are more resilient against e.g. climate impacts and pests and offer more robust ecosystems to

- deliver regulating services.
- Converting large urban forests not originally designed for high biodiversity is very challenging and **necessitates time and adequate knowledge and resources**.
- **A short, animated video (5-6 minutes) is sometimes a better argument than a long talk** to convince and inspire people to take biodiversity in NBS into account and to translate complex scientific insights. They can be used in training sessions to stakeholders, including local and regional politicians and for the wider public
- There are simple and effective ways to increase biodiversity in urban parks, but these will **change the aesthetics of a traditional urban park**. Training of park managers, educating and communicating with the public and integrating biodiversity-friendly management practices into parks to cater for both nature and people are essential elements.
- **NBS objectives need to include goals to support biological diversity** and ecosystem conservation, coupled with measurable targets in order to avoid green-washing.
- There are limits to the standardisation of high-quality NBS, but **quality standards relevant to the different types of specific NBS interventions are essential** to secure high quality NBS.
- **Main barriers to securing high ecological quality in NBS include cultural barriers** - people's perception of biodiversity (good /bad) which requires the need for education and capacity building; the need for significant investment to transform past grey solutions to NBS and the trade-offs between e.g. biodiversity and carbon sequestration.

Concluding remarks

This webinar focused on different axes on improving urban ecosystem restoration in both China, Europe and Latin America: economics; policy, governance and institutional issues; education and awareness raising; social aspects; environmental aspects and ecological quality in urban nature restoration. These axes are crucial in fostering urban transitions

through a systemic change in how cities are operated and lived in. A number of tools, findings and approaches have been showed during these two days and we hope this will serve as an inspiration, prove useful in your work be it in academia, public services or private institutions.

Do follow the projects CLEARINGHOUSE, CONEXUS, INTERLACE and REGREEN to learn more. You can find all material from this webinar (recording, slides and resources list) as well as all outputs (papers, deliverables etc.) from the four projects gathered on <https://zenodo.org/communities/clearinghouse-conexus-interlace-regreen/>.

Project websites:

<https://regreen-project.eu>

<https://nature-solutions.eu>

<https://www.conexusnbs.com>

<https://clearinghouseproject.eu>

<https://www.interlace-project.eu>

<https://interlace-hub.com>